

0.01



Baniwa Central Isana

Koripako Upper Isana

Baniwa Lower Isana

Koripako Guania

Tariana Vaupes

*Northeastern JC*

Achagua

*Yukunic cluster*

Piapoco

*Nuclear JC*

Kabiyari

Yukuna

*Kauishanic Cluster*

Passe

Resigaro

Yumana

Kauixana